

Stoichiometric and Structural Studies of the Complexes of 3d Metals with 2-Hydroxyphenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide

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Interaction of some 3d metals with 2-hydroxyphenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide has been studied by different physicochemical methods. Electrometric studies and chemical analysis gave 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio. Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal chelates are paramagnetic, showing magnetic moment values corresponding to the spin values of unpaired electrons. All these metal chelates are high spin, having octahedral stereochemistry except the Cu^{II} complex which has square planar structure. IR studies showed M-N, M-S bonding and coordinated water.

INTERACTION between Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ag^I, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II} with benzamidothiosemicarbazide¹⁻⁶ were reported earlier. In this communication, the results of our physicochemical studies on the composition and structural characteristics of 2-hydroxyphenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide and Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} have been summarised.

Experimental

2-Hydroxyphenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide (OH-BTSC) was prepared by the reported method⁷ and its solution was prepared in 80% ethanol. Fresh solution of OH-BTSC was always used. Stock solutions of chlorides of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and acetate of Cu^{II} (B.D.H., AnalaR) were prepared by dissolving their salts in air free double distilled water. The strength of these solutions was determined by standard methods.

Conductometric titrations of OH-BTSC against metal ions were carried out to determine the stoichiometry of the complexes. A series of mixture of solutions according to monovariation method were prepared and the observed conductance was plotted against the concentration of metal or ligand. The inflection corresponds to the M : L ratio. Moreover, a series of mixtures using equimolar solutions (0.02 M), keeping the amount of ligand constant (4.0 ml) and varying that of the metal (1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0 and 4.0 ml) were prepared. The total volume (30 ml) of each solution was kept constant and titrated against 0.04 M KOH and corresponding conductances were noted. The corrected conductance values were plotted against moles of KOH. Blank titration for metal and ligand was also carried out. Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge with dip type conductivity cell was used for determining the conductance.

Amperometric titrations, both direct and reverse were carried out at constant potential (-0.4 V), using 0.02 M solutions of metal and ligand in presence of 0.2 M KCl as supporting electrolyte and 0.01% fresh solution of gelatin as maximum suppressor. The diffusion currents were corrected for dilution and plotted against the volume of metal or ligand to give M : L ratio. Toshniwal CLO2A manual polarograph was used.

Equimolar solutions of metal salts and OH-BTSC were mixed with stirring in 1 : 1 ratio. The resulting solutions were concentrated, cooled, filtered and recrystallised (hot methanol for Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II}, dioxan for Co^{II}, and chloroform for Cu^{II} complex). The complexes were dried in vacuum desiccator and were analysed for elements (Table 1).

The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were measured on Gouy's balance model C Meltzovic type H16 at 25° corrected for diamagnetic contribution (Table 1). The IR spectra of the ligand and their complexes in KBr were recorded on Beckman IR 20.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary observations revealed that aqueous solutions of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} mixed with the solution of OH-BTSC gave yellow, buff, wine red, dark brown, brownish black and brownish yellow precipitates, respectively. These precipitates are easily separable on standing or concentrating the solution and more quickly on increasing the pH ≈ 9 of the solution. Furthermore, the complex formation was stronger in higher pH range. Results of conductometric titrations of metal-ligand mixture against KOH showed the liberation of protons during complexation. Blank titrations of ligand against KOH gave inflection at 1 : 2 stoichiometric ratio *i.e.* corresponding to the

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Complex	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)						Metal	μ_{eff} B.M.
	C	H	O	N	S	Cl		
Cr(C ₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₄ SOl)	27.86 (27.68)	3.48 (3.48)	18.41 (18.41)	16.11 (16.11)	9.22 (9.22)	10.20 (10.20)	14.96 (14.95)	3.75
Mn(C ₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₄ S)	28.84 (28.84)	4.24 (4.24)	24.00 (24.01)	16.91 (16.81)	9.61 (9.62)	—	16.46 (16.49)	6.00
Fe(C ₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₄ SOl)	27.25 (27.38)	3.42 (3.44)	18.11 (18.21)	15.90 (15.93)	9.10 (9.12)	10.22 (10.09)	15.99 (15.89)	5.82
Co(C ₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₄ S)	28.89 (28.49)	4.24 (4.19)	23.67 (23.73)	16.71 (16.61)	9.59 (9.51)	—	17.26 (17.48)	4.89
Ni(C ₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₄ S)	28.35 (28.51)	4.23 (4.19)	23.82 (23.74)	16.65 (16.62)	9.48 (9.51)	—	17.49 (17.42)	3.00
Cu(C ₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₄ S)	31.85 (31.42)	3.27 (3.30)	15.70 (15.70)	18.29 (18.31)	10.51 (10.49)	—	20.80 (20.78)	1.76

liberation of two hydrogen from one mole of the ligand.

Normal conductometric curves (monovariation method) were obtained for all these metals. In all these cases, sharp breaks corresponding to 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio were obtained for both direct and reverse titrations. Titration curves in which metal was 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5 and 3.0 ml showed two breaks, the first corresponding to 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio and the second was due to the neutralisation of unused excess of ligand in 1 : 2 ratio, as was obtained in the titration of the ligand alone. It was also observed that titration curves in which metal was 4.0 ml (1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio) showed a single break. Up to the first break, the increase in conductance was due to the replacement of metal ions by K⁺ and the H⁺ from the ligand being removed as water by interaction with OH⁻ of KOH. Thereafter, up to the second break, the higher increase in conductance values were due to the formation of more ionisable K-salt of the ligand, and beyond the second break, the sharp increase was due to free KOH.

In the amperometric titrations, the potential of the d.m.e. (-0.4 V) was selected from the plateaux of OH-BTSC ($E_{1/2} = -0.12$ V). Normal curves were obtained breaking at the same stoichiometric points. Results of chemical analysis (Table 1) further supported the stoichiometric ratios as obtained by electrometric studies and on this basis molecular formulae were suggested for these compounds.

All these complexes were found paramagnetic with magnetic moment values corresponding to the spin only values for unpaired electrons. These values are in fair agreement with the values found in other complexes.

A sharp band at 3555 cm⁻¹ (phenolic OH) in the ir spectra of the ligand disappears in the spectra of metal complexes suggesting loss of phenolic hydrogen on complex formation and establishing a bond between metal and phenolic oxygen in these complexes.

The strong bands in OH-BTSC at 3330, 3285 and at 3200 cm⁻¹ are due to the NH and NH₂ stretch-

ing vibrations. In the spectra of metal complexes these vibrations shift to higher region at 3400-3525 cm⁻¹, suggesting that hydrazine group is not involved in the complex formation⁸⁻¹⁰. Furthermore, the band 3330 cm⁻¹ for the ligand appears as sharp broad band at 3430-3500, 3435-3480, 3440-3525, 3400-3480, 3400-3510 and 3410-3520 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal chelates, respectively and suggests that this vibration is affected by some vibrational modes probably -OH of the attached water molecule¹⁰. However, one weak band at 3660-3675 cm⁻¹ of metal complexes confirms coordinated water. This band is assigned to the antisymmetric and symmetric O-H stretching modes.

The sharp band at 1610 cm⁻¹ observed in the OH-BTSC spectra is due to the bending vibrations of amino and amide groups. This band is moved to higher frequency region at 1610-1620 cm⁻¹ with increased intensity for the metal complexes. This indicates that the amido nitrogen is not involved in bond formation and is due to the symmetric stretching modes of coordinated water¹⁰.

The sharp bands in OH-BTSC at 1325, 1300, 710 and 690 cm⁻¹ are due to C=S stretching frequencies. Similar assignments have been made for thioacetamides, thiosemicarbazides and other thio compounds^{9,11,12}. The band at 1060 cm⁻¹ for C=S stretching has been reported in xanthates^{8,13}. This band in OH-BTSC occurs at 1075 cm⁻¹. The intensities of these vibrations are decreased and shifted to lower frequencies at 1315, 1275, 1060, 660 and 610 cm⁻¹ in Cr^{III}; 1310, 1270, 1065, 670 and 605 cm⁻¹ in Mn^{II}; 1310, 1265, 1055, 670 and 610 cm⁻¹ in Fe^{III}; 1295, 1265, 1040, 675 and 615 cm⁻¹ in Co^{II}; 1300, 1260, 1060, 670 and 610 cm⁻¹ in Ni^{II}; 1290, 1255, 1050, 675 and 600 cm⁻¹ in Cu^{II} complexes, confirming metal-sulphur bands.

The sharp band at 1200 cm⁻¹ in OH-BTSC is due to NCS bend, NH₂ rock and NH₂ deformation. This band appears at 1155-1170 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. The lowering of frequency clearly indicates the involvement of imido nitrogen in the bonding with metal.

Furthermore, new medium bands at $465\text{-}520\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for M-N and shoulders at $270\text{-}298\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for M-S, are assigned. On the basis of the above informations, following structures have been assigned to these complexes.

M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} ;
 Z = H₂O for Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} ; Cl for Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}.

M = Cu^{II} ;
 X = CONH, Y = NH.NH₂

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